

1 **The gene encoding HER2, ERBB2, is differentially expressed in the mammary glands of BRCA1**
2 **mutant humans.**

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7 We studied growth factor signaling in cells and tissues with genetic deficiency in BRCA1/2. We report here
8 activation of HER2 in the mammary glands of humans with BRCA1 mutation.

9 Citations

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